

Assessment of the Crisis Communication Strategies of University of Benin, Edo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The researcher assessed the crisis communication strategies in the University of Benin, Edo State. The objectives of the study were, among others, to know the extent to which university of Benin engages in crisis communication and identify the strategies used by the university to engage in crisis in communication. The study was anchored on the contingency theory of strategic conflict management and situational crisis communication theory. The researcher used the survey research design, using questionnaire as data collection instrument. From a population of 77,000 students and 8,000 staff, a sample size of 749 (382 students and 367 staff) respondents was arrived at using Krejcie & Morgan's sample size formula. The data collected were analysed using simple percentages to provide answers to the research questions. The findings showed that the university of Benin engages moderately in crisis communication, as majority of staff and students agreed that the university communicates during crises. It was also found that the university employs a mix of press releases, social media and emails for crisis communication, while the university's crisis communication was found to be moderately effective. The researcher concluded that crisis communication at the university of Benin is active but not fully effective. Based on the findings and conclusion, the researcher recommended that the University of Benin should adopt a proactive crisis communication approach, ensuring that timely, anticipatory messages are released before misinformation spreads and also integrate student-friendly platforms like WhatsApp and Instagram into its official communication channels to increase reach and engagement, amongst others.

Keywords: Assessment, Crises, Communication, Strategies, University of Benin

Introduction

Crisis is inevitable and communication is very important for every organisation, during difficult times. Tertiary institutions, including the University of Benin (UNIBEN) are no exception. As centres of learning and growth, they face various problems, such as strikes, security issues, health crises, shortage of water, lack of transportation and so on. To handle these situations well, they need strong crisis communication strategies. A well-organised system helps the institution stay stable and continue operating, even during tough times (Ogbemi, 2011; Oyibota & Asemah, 2024).

According to Okoye (2013), crisis communication means sharing important information with people during emergencies. It involves sending accurate, clear, and timely messages to manage the problem, reduce harm and build trust. This is not just about reacting when a crisis happens but also includes preparing for risks, being ready, and reviewing what happened after the crisis is over. Asemah-Ibrahim, Nwaoboli & Asemah (2022b) note that individuals and governments experience crises from time to time and such crisis could attract bad publicity which can be very damaging to their image. Crisis has existed for as long as human societies have functioned. Throughout history, communities, businesses, and governments have faced unexpected events that disrupt normal operations (Asemah-Ibrahim, Nwaoboli & Asemah (2022). Today, crisis communication is a key part of public relations and corporate management. Oyibotha & Asemah (2024) aver that crisis communication can be challenging for tertiary institutions in Nigeria. One big issue is that many institutions are usually reactive, rather than being proactive. In most cases, their staff do not have proper training. Most universities do not have teams that are trained to handle emergencies. Research has shown that these gaps are due to inadequate preparation, lack of resources, and poor stakeholder engagement strategies. This has raised concerns about the resilience of Nigerian universities in handling crises effectively. Notably, UNIBEN like other Nigerian universities have dealt with several crises in the past. These include student protests, strikes, security concerns, and the challenges of the COVID-19 pandemic. That aside, these challenges at UNIBEN show the larger problems Nigerian universities face with crisis communication.

The University of Benin, like many tertiary institutions in Nigeria, have faced several crises in recent years. These include industrial actions, security threat and others challenges in the post COVID-19 pandemic era. Despite the critical role of effective communication during such times, there have been concerns about the university's ability to provide timely and accurate information to its stakeholders. Inadequate crisis communication can lead to misinformation, panic and a breakdown of trust between the institution and its stakeholders. With this in view, it, therefore, becomes important to evaluate UNIBEN's crisis communication strategies.

Research Objectives

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Determine the extent to which university of Benin engage in crisis communication.
2. Identify the strategies used by university of Benin to engage in crisis in communication.
3. Find out the level of effectiveness of the crisis communication of University of Benin.

Theoretical Framework

Contingency Theory of Strategic Conflict Management

The contingency theory of strategic conflict management was developed by Cameron, Wilcox, Reber & Shin in 2008. This theory holds that crisis communication is not fixed

but rather flexible. Organisations do not use the same approach for every crisis. Instead, they decide on their response based on different factors (Asemah, Nwammuo & Nkwam-Uwaoma, 2022). The theory places crisis communication on a continuum, with pure advocacy on one end and pure accommodation on the other. Pure advocacy means the organisation fully defends itself, denying any wrongdoing and standing by its actions. Pure accommodation means the organisation fully accepts responsibility, apologises, and makes changes to correct the situation. In between these two extremes, there are various mixed strategies, depending on how serious the crisis is and who is affected. The contingency theory of strategic conflict management is appropriate for assessing the crisis communication strategies of the University of Benin. This flexibility makes the theory useful in analysing the university's decision-making process during crises.

Situational Crisis Communication Theory

The situational crisis communication theory was developed by Timothy Coombs in 2007 and he argued that the response to a crisis should be based on the specific nature of the crisis and the organisation's previous reputation. It emphasises that different types of crises require different communication strategies and that an organisation's reputation before the crisis plays a significant role in how the crisis should be managed (Eke, Alid & Asemah, 2024). The theory outlines several strategies, including denial, diminishment, rebuilding, and bolstering, which can be employed depending on the type and severity of the crisis. It is relevant to this study as it offers a structured way to handle crises effectively. It helps organisations, like UNIBEN, identify the type of crisis they are facing and understand how their existing reputation affects public perception.

Conceptual and Literature Review

According to Coombs (2022), crisis communication is the process of sharing information during an emergency or difficult situation. It involves passing on messages to people who are affected, such as employees, students, customers, or the public. The aim is to provide clear and accurate information to manage the situation, reduce confusion and build trust. Okoye (2013) asserts that crisis communication is one of the new frontiers of modern management which must be explored and mastered for the reason that crisis exist, even when they have not manifested. The main objective of crisis communication is to be well prepared for crisis, ensure rapid and adequate response to crisis, maintaining clear lines of communication in the event of crisis and agreeing on rules for crisis termination. The response, therefore, include: crisis prevention, crisis assessment, crisis handling and crisis termination (Oyibotha *et al* 2023). Crisis communication can, therefore, be seen as the process by which an organisation communicates and deals with a major event that threatens to harm the organisation, its stakeholders or the general public.

The effective application of various communication strategies can help an organisation respond to crises while maintaining stakeholder trust and minimising reputational damage. Business Insider (2024); Pumble (2024) and Business.com (nd) outlined the following as key strategies of Crisis communication.

1. **Developing a Crisis Communication Plan:** One of the first and most critical strategies in crisis communication is developing a crisis communication plan (Asemah Akase & Nkwam-Uwaoma, 2018). The plan ensures that the organisation can act quickly

and coherently in response to a crisis, reducing confusion and improving coordination. A detailed plan allows organisations to anticipate possible issues and prepare solutions in advance.

2. **Assembling a Crisis Management Team:** A crisis management team is important for ensuring a smooth and organised response to a crisis. This team must consist of individuals from various departments, such as public relations, legal, and operations, as each department brings different expertise that may be necessary in handling the situation.

3. **Communicating honestly and transparently:** Honesty and transparency are essential in crisis communication. Organisations must provide accurate, truthful information to all stakeholders, as this builds trust and helps maintain a positive relationship during a crisis. When an organisation tries to withhold information or provide misleading updates, it can create a situation where trust is further eroded, resulting in long-term damage to its reputation.

4. **Ensuring Clear and Concise Messaging:** During crisis, it is important that the message is clear and concise. A well-crafted message is easy to understand and free from jargon, ensuring that it can be understood by a wide audience. Thus, crisis communication should focus on simplifying messages, ensuring they are direct and understandable to all involved.

5. **Appropriate Communication Channels:** Choosing the right communication channels during a crisis is vital for reaching the intended audience efficiently. Different stakeholders may engage with different types of media; for instance, younger audiences might prefer social media platforms, while traditional media might be more suitable for older demographics (Pumble.com, 2024.).

6. **Monitoring and Managing Social Media:** Social media plays a major role in modern crisis communication. Monitoring social media platforms allows organisations to stay informed about public sentiment and respond quickly to any misinformation or negative feedback. Effective management of social media helps the organisation communicate directly with the public, addressing concerns and providing real-time updates.

7. **Providing Regular Updates:** In times of crisis, stakeholders need regular updates to stay informed and to manage their expectations. Keeping all parties updated on the status of the situation helps reduce uncertainty and builds confidence that the organisation is actively working to resolve the issue. Regular communication ensures that stakeholders are not left in the dark and can make informed decisions based on the latest information.

8. **Showing Empathy and Support:** During a crisis, showing empathy can impact how stakeholders perceive the organisation. Empathetic communication demonstrates

that the organisation is not only concerned with resolving the crisis but also cares about the well-being of those impacted. This human element of crisis communication creates goodwill and helps strengthen bonds with the public.

9. **Evaluating and Learning from the Crisis:** After the crisis has been managed, it is important to evaluate the response and learn from the experience. Conducting a post-crisis analysis helps the organisation identify what strategies were effective and where improvements can be made.

Crisis communication plays a crucial role in organisational management by helping institutions effectively manage emergencies, protect their reputation, and maintain trust among their stakeholders. During crises, organisations face the challenge of providing clear, accurate, and timely information to minimise confusion and prevent misinformation. Coombs (2022) notes that crisis communication involves strategic communication efforts aimed at protecting an organisation's reputation and ensuring it continues to function smoothly even in times of trouble.

Fearn-Banks (2016) states that one of the primary roles of crisis communication in organisational management is reputation protection. Organisations are usually judged by how well they respond to crises. When an organisation communicates transparently and promptly during a crisis, it shows accountability and credibility. By providing reliable information and acknowledging the crisis, organisations can control the narrative and prevent the spread of false information. This approach helps to maintain the organisation's image and reputation even in the midst of a challenging situation. Coombs & Holladay (2012) point out that crisis communication is essential for maintaining trust and relationships with stakeholders. Stakeholders include employees, customers, investors, government agencies, the media, and the general public.

Furthermore, crisis communication also supports organisational resilience and continuity. Ulmer, Sellnow, & Seeger (2018) argue that well-prepared crisis communication plans enable organisations to respond quickly and effectively, minimising disruptions and allowing for a smooth recovery process. Fraustino & Liu (2017) highlight that effective crisis communication provides a platform for dialogue and feedback, allowing organisations to address concerns, clarify misunderstandings, and promote cooperation towards resolving conflicts. Addressing issues in a constructive manner reduces the chances of escalation and helps restore normalcy. That aside, providing accurate and timely information helps to calm people and reduces the spread of rumours. Fearn-Banks (2016) explains that when organisations remain silent during crises, people tend to fill the information gap with speculations, which can worsen the situation. Therefore, an active communication approach is necessary to maintain order and control.

Oyibotha & Asemah (2024) conducted a study titled the adoption and utilisation of social media for crisis management in selected tertiary institutions in Edo State, Nigeria. The researchers sought to examine the extent to which social media are used for information dissemination and crisis management in tertiary institutions. A survey method was used to collect data from staff and students in the selected institutions. The findings showed that social media play a significant role in crisis management, as it facilitates effective communication and interaction among stakeholders during crises. The study revealed that email was the most frequently used social media tool in these

institutions. It concluded that understanding the functionalities of social media is essential for enhancing crisis communication. It recommended improving internet infrastructure and providing training to maximise the use of social media platforms for effective crisis management operations. The similarity between this study and the present study is that both are focused on how communication is managed within educational institutions during crisis.

Methodology

The research design is survey and structured questionnaire as data collection instrument. This method is useful in gathering information that can be measured and used to understand the relationship between different factors. The population for this study comprises both academic and non-academic staff of the University of Benin (UNIBEN), as well as undergraduate students of the institution. According to data obtained from the university's help desk for the 2023/2024 academic session, UNIBEN has a total of 77,000 undergraduate students and 8,000 staff members. These groups collectively form the focus of this study. The sample size for this study is 749 (382 students and 367 staff) calculated using Krejcie & Morgan's formula. The study used a multi-stage sampling technique to administer copies of questionnaire on both staff and students. This approach was chosen because it allows the researcher to select respondents in several stages using different methods.

For the student, in the first stage, five faculties were randomly selected from UNIBEN (Arts, Social Sciences, Education, Management Sciences and Life Sciences). In the second stage, departments were chosen from these faculties using the purposive sampling technique. The departments selected include Mass Communication and Theatre Arts from the Faculty of Arts, Accounting from the Faculty of Management Sciences, Educational Foundation from the Faculty of Education, as well as Public Administration from the Faculty of Social Sciences and Science Laboratory Technology from the Faculty of Life Sciences. In the third stage, the students were grouped by academic levels (1st, 2nd, 3rd, and 4th years). Then, 91 students each were selected from level 1 and 2, while 100 students each were selected each from level 3 and 4. The respondents were then chosen randomly using the simple random sampling technique.

For the staff, in the first stage, the entire population of staff at the University of Benin was stratified into two major categories: academic staff and non-academic staff. This initial stratification ensured that the sample reflected the diverse organisational structure and functional roles within the institution. In the second stage, clusters were formed within each stratum. For academic staff, clustering was based on faculty affiliation, while for non-academic staff, clustering was done according to administrative or technical units. This clustering allowed for practical and systematic selection within defined organisational units. In the third stage, a random selection of clusters was conducted using simple random sampling, ensuring that each faculty or department had an equal chance of inclusion. Thus, 5 faculties (Faculty of Arts, Faculty of Social Sciences, Faculty of Education, Faculty of Management Sciences and Faculty of Life Sciences) and 5 administrative/technical units (Registry, Student Affairs, Estate & Works, Exams & Records and Admissions Office) were selected. In the fourth stage, a convenience sampling method was employed to administer copies of questionnaire on the

sample size of 367 staff members across the selected clusters. However, of the total sampled and returned copies of questionnaire, 645 (86.1%) copies were successfully validated for use.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1: Crisis Communication Efforts are Promptly Initiated when Crises Occur

Variables	Staff (%)	Students (%)
Strongly agree	45 (14.9%)	47 (13.7%)
Agree	57 (18.9%)	65 (18.9%)
Neutral	53 (17.5%)	61 (17.8%)
Disagree	75 (24.8%)	83 (24.2%)
Strongly disagree	72 (23.8%)	87 (25.4%)
Total	302 (100%)	343 (100%)

Table 1 shows that majority of the respondents (staff 48.6%; student 49.6%) believes that crisis communication efforts of the University are not promptly initiated. This shows that although some efforts are made, many students and staff feel the university is not quick enough in its crisis communication.

Table 2: Social Media Platform used to obtain Information during Crisis in UNIBEN

Variables	Staff (%)	Students (%)
Facebook	41 (13.6%)	51 (14.9%)
WhatsApp	89 (29.5%)	101 (29.5%)
X (Twitter)	61 (20.2%)	69 (20.1%)
Instagram	55 (18.2%)	63 (18.4%)
TikTok	56 (18.5%)	59 (17.2%)
Total	302 (100%)	343 (100%)

Table 2 reveals that WhatsApp is the platform mostly used to obtain information during crisis in UNIBEN. This shows that the respondents are exposed to the use of social media during crisis in UNIBEN.

Table 3: Frequency at which the University uses Press Releases to address Crisis Situations

Variables	Staff (%)	Students (%)
Very Frequently	41 (13.6%)	49 (14.3%)
Occasionally	103 (34.1%)	131 (38.2%)
Neutral	55 (18.2%)	57 (16.6%)
Rarely	63 (20.9%)	63 (18.4%)
Never	40 (13.2%)	43 (12.5%)
Total	302 (100%)	343 (100%)

The data in the table show that the university occasionally uses press releases during crises. This shows that press releases are a known and recognised method of communication during crises at the university.

Table 4: Extent to which Email and Newsletters are used to provide Crisis-Related Update

Variables	Staff (%)	Students (%)
Very high	29 (9.6%)	33 (9.6%)
High	41 (13.6%)	47 (13.7%)
Neutral	49 (16.2%)	57 (16.6%)
Low	85 (28.1%)	95 (27.7%)
Very low	98 (32.5%)	111 (32.4%)
Total	302 (100%)	343 (100%)

Table 4 reveals that a combined majority of the respondents (60.4%) believe email and newsletters are not widely used to provide crisis related update. This data indicate that email and newsletters are underutilised in crisis communication efforts at the University of Benin.

Table 5: Effectiveness of University Benin’s Communication Approach in preventing Escalation of Crises

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very effective	38	9.9%
Effective	42	11.0%
Neutral	21	5.5%
Slightly effective	120	31.5%
Not effective	160	42.1%
Total	381	100%

Table 5 highlights that a significant proportion (42.1%) expressed dissatisfaction with the effectiveness of the University of Benin’s communication approach in preventing crises from escalating.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from table 1 provide valuable insights into the extent to which the University of Benin engages in crisis communication. Table 1 reveals that a significant proportion of the respondents (60.7%) agreed that crisis communication efforts are not promptly initiated when crises occur. This indicates a perceived delay or insufficiency in the university’s initial response to crises, which may negatively impact the effectiveness of crisis management and stakeholder confidence. Hence, the University of Benin demonstrates moderate extent of engagement in crisis communication. However, the perceived lack of promptness in initiating communication points to a crucial area for development.

The data in tables 2, 3 and 4 reveal a variety of strategies employed by the University of Benin to engage in crisis communication. According to the data from table 2, the most commonly used platforms for receiving crisis-related information among staff and students are WhatsApp (29.5%), Twitter (X) (20.1–20.2%) and Instagram (18.2–18.4%), indicating a strong reliance on social media. Despite this wide channel usage, table 4 reveals a major gap in the use of emails and newsletters, which are traditionally expected in institutional communication. A significant number of respondents rated the use of email and newsletters as “low” or “very low” (60.6% of staff and 60.1% of

students), suggesting that these formal channels are underutilised during crises. This raises concerns about the university's ability to maintain a formal, traceable and professional communication record during emergencies, especially for messages requiring detailed clarification or follow-up. In terms of traditional press release usage, table 3 shows that only 13.6% of staff and 14.3% of students believe press releases are issued "very frequently," with the majority indicating it happens only "occasionally" or "rarely." This suggests that while press releases are part of the university's crisis communication toolkit, they are not the dominant method and may not be relied upon for urgent dissemination of information. Empirically, these findings resonate strongly with the study by Oyibotha & Asemah (2024), which found that social media are a critical tool for crisis communication in tertiary institutions in Edo State. As in the case of Uniben, WhatsApp and email were frequently used. However, while email topped usage in the referenced study, it appears significantly underutilised at Uniben, suggesting an area for strategic improvement. Thus, the University of Benin adopts a layered crisis communication strategy, using a mix of social media, informal student networks, official websites and occasional press releases.

The findings presented in table 5 reveal a generally low perception of the effectiveness of the University of Benin's crisis communication approach. A combined total of 73.6% of respondents rated the university's communication efforts as either slightly effective (31.5%) or not effective (42.1%) in preventing the escalation of crises. Only a small proportion of respondents—very effective (9.9%) and effective (11.0%)—felt that the communication strategies in place are successful in managing crisis situations. These results suggest a significant gap in how the university's crisis communication is perceived in terms of timeliness, reach, clarity and impact. This perceived ineffectiveness may stem from an overreliance on formal communication channels such as press releases and internal memos, as identified in earlier findings, while underutilising more immediate and interactive platforms like social media and emergency alerts. The lack of responsiveness or failure to engage stakeholders in a timely and accessible manner could contribute to communication breakdowns during crisis events, reducing the university's ability to contain or de-escalate situations swiftly. Thus, the data show that the University of Benin's crisis communication strategy is largely viewed as inadequate by its stakeholders.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study concludes that the university's crisis communication approach demonstrates moderate engagement and potential for impact, but requires significant improvements in speed, strategy and inclusiveness to be fully effective in both crisis management and conflict resolution. On the basis of the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations are made:

1. The University of Benin should adopt a proactive crisis communication approach, ensuring that timely, anticipatory messages are released before misinformation spreads.
2. The University of Benin should integrate student-friendly platforms like WhatsApp and Instagram into its official communication channels to increase reach and engagement.

References

- Asemah, E. S., Akase, T. M. & Nkwam-Uwaoma, A. O. (2018). *Business of international public relations and advertising*. Jos: Matkol Press.
- Asemah, E. S., Nwammuo, A. N. & Nkwam-Uwaoma, A. O. A. (2022). *Theories and models of communication (2nd ed.)*. Jos: Jos University Press.
- Asemah-Ibrahim, M. O., Nwaoboli, E. P. & Asemah, E. S. (2022). Corporate social responsibility as a strategy for crisis management by organisations. *GVU Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 7(3), 148–159.
- Business.com. (n.d.). 6 effective strategies for communication in a crisis. Retrieved from <https://www.business.com/articles/effective-crisis-communication-strategies/>
- Business Insider. (2024, July 20). CrowdStrike's crisis management strategy holds lessons for all companies. Retrieved from <https://www.businessinsider.com/crowdstrike-it-outage-key-lessons-on-crisis-management-pr-disasters-2024-7>
- Coombs, W. T. (2007). Protecting organisation reputations during a crisis: The development and application of situational crisis communication theory. *Corporate Reputation Review*, 10(3), 163–176.
- Coombs, W. T. (2022). *Ongoing crisis communication: Planning, managing and responding (6th ed.)*. New York, NY: Sage Publications.
- Coombs, W. T. & Holladay, S. J. (2012). Comparing apology to equivalent crisis response strategies: Clarifying apology's role and value in crisis communication. *Public Relations Review*, 34(3), 252–257.
- Eke, M. C., Alid, U. & Asemah, E. S. (2024). Crisis communication strategies for navigating reputation management in the digital age. In E. S. Asemah (Ed.), *Case Studies in Public Relations, Advertising and Behavioural Change Communication* (pp. 23–33). Enugu: Franklead Printing and Publishing Co.
- Fearn-Banks, K. (2016). *Crisis communications: A casebook approach*. UK: Routledge.
- Fraustino, J. D. & Liu, B. F. (2017). Toward more audience-oriented approaches to crisis communication and social media research. In L. Austin & Y. Jin (Eds.), *Social Media and Crisis Communication* (pp. 129–140). New York, NY: Routledge.
- Ogbemi, B. O. (2014). *Public relations: Principles, practice and management*. Lagos: Amfitop Books.
- Ogbemi, O. B. (2011). Public perception of the corporate image of the University of Benin Teaching Hospital (UBTH). *Journal of Business Studies and Technology Development*, 6(2), 129–139.
- Okoye, M. (2013). *Public relations in crisis management*. Lagos: Tough Teachers Publishers.
- Oyibotha, P. H. & Asemah, E. S. (2024). Adoption and utilisation of social media for crisis management in select tertiary institutions in Edo State Nigeria. In E. S. Asemah (Ed.), *Case studies in public relations, advertising and behavioural change* (pp. 90–98). Enugu: Franklead Printing and Publishing Company.
- Pumble. (2024). What is crisis communication? Strategies and examples for effective communication. Retrieved from <https://pumble.com/blog/crisis-communication/>
- Ulmer, R. R., Sellnow, T. L. & Seeger, M. W. (2018). *Effective crisis communication: Moving from crisis to opportunity*. London: Sage Publications.